

Variance of Fourier Transform of a Gaussian and the Schrodinger Equation

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In (1), we discussed how various Liouville-Continuity equation approaches of deriving the Schrodinger equation starting with a classical density $d(x,t)$ ultimately create an energy conservation equation and assume $S = -Et + px$, where E is the bound state energy and p , the center-of-mass momentum (usually 0) of the bound system. Thus, the whole Liouville-continuity approach seems to be to provide an expression for average kinetic energy.

We argued in (1), that if $S = -Et + px$ applies to the center of mass of a bound system, it also applies to a free particle. In particular, d/dt partial and d/dx are used in the Liouville approaches to obtain $-E$ and p so one may write the math eigenfunction $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ for a free particle. Using $\exp(ipx)$ for the single particle in a $V(x)$ as a probability leads to a prescription for KE ave = $\{ \text{Sum over } p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p)\exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \}$.

Thus, whatever approach introduced in the Liouville-continuity derivation must be consistent with $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability. In this note, we examine specifically the approach used in (2). (2) introduces the axiom: $\langle \Delta p \Delta p \rangle \langle \Delta x \Delta x \rangle = \hbar^2/4$. We argue that this is satisfied for a Gaussian probability for $P(x)$ with $P(p)$ being the Fourier transform of this Gaussian. (The variance of a Gaussian is 1/variance of the Fourier transform.) Thus, the axiom used in (1) explicitly uses $\exp(ipx)$ which is consistent with the $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ approach discussed above and essentially contains the idea of quantum mechanics, i.e. the notion of $\exp(ipx)$ describing the p dependence of a free particle. In particular, if one has a Gaussian $P(x)$, then its Fourier transform is: $\text{Sum over } p \exp(-ipx) P(x)$ or $P(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. The square root of a Gaussian is also a Gaussian so $W(x) = \sqrt{P(x)} = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. For a single particle, one has $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ so that $a(p)a(p)\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1/\sqrt{L} = d(x,t)$, where L is length.

The starting point of (1) is to consider evaluating essentially $d(x,t) \langle dp dp \rangle$ where $\langle dp dp \rangle$ is a fluctuation above the mean. To do so, however, $\langle dx dx \rangle$ is calculated with $d(x,t) = \exp(\text{entropy})$. The entropy is expanded to second order in dx to create a Gaussian and the Gaussian variance obtained. Then $\langle dp dp \rangle$ is taken to be 1/ variance from the axiom of (2). This ultimately leads to a $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ expression for $\langle dp dp \rangle / 2m$ which is acting as average kinetic energy, but we argue that this result is already anticipated by noting that the axiom of (2) assumes $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ are Gaussians and one is the Fourier transform of the other. In other words, the a priori axiom of (2) contains quantum mechanics and is consistent with the $S(x,t) = -Et + px$ later used. One may obtain the entire quantum result from simply using $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ for a free particle as argued in (1).

Liouville-Continuity Equation Approach to Deriving the Schrodinger Equation

We noted in (1) that there are numerous derivations of the Schrodinger equation using the Liouville-Continuity approach in the literature. We argued that all of these approaches make use of the following

- A. They take $\text{grad} \cdot v$ density in the continuity equation and suggest that $p(x,t)/m = d/dx \text{ partial } S(x,t)$. Later, $d/dt \text{ partial } S(x,t)$ is taken to be $-E$, the bound state energy. This leads to: $S = -Et + px$, i.e. the classical action for the center of mass of the bound state. $d/dt \text{ partial}$ and $d/dx \text{ partial}$ act on this action to bring in $-E$ and p so one may just as well introduce the eigenfunction $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and use this as a probability for a free particle and then calculate the average kinetic energy for a potential $V(x)$ using:

$$\text{KE ave} = \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((2))$$

This, however, is not done in these approaches. Rather, separate assumptions are made to obtain a conservation of energy equation from the combined Liouville-continuity equation such that an average kinetic term arises. This average kinetic energy, however, is equivalent to ((2)) and so we argued in (1) that there is no need for the Liouville-continuity equation or the special conditions needed to create ((2)).

Here, we examine specifically the special condition used in (2) to derive the Schrodinger equation using the Liouville-continuity equation approach.

Approach of (2)

The main feature of (2) is to present the axiom:

$$\langle dp \ dp \rangle \langle dx \ dx \rangle = \hbar \ \hbar/4 \quad (\text{We set } \hbar=1) \quad ((3))$$

Here dp is a slight variation in p and dx in x . $\langle dp \ dp \rangle$ is essentially a variance.

The main point we wish to make is that the axiom ((3)) is satisfied by having $P(x)$ be a Gaussian and $P(p)$, its Fourier transform. In such a case, one has inverse variances/2 and ((3)) is satisfied. This, however, means that $\exp(ipx)$ is in the picture and this is exactly the free particle x part of the wavefunction. Thus, we argue that quantum mechanics is already introduced at this point, i.e. at the beginning through the axiom ((3)) without any need for a Liouville-continuity equation. Furthermore, this is consistent with the $p(x,t) = dS/dx \text{ partial}$ picture which is linked to $\exp(ipx)$.

To see in more detail the approach of (2), one may notice that an explicit Gaussian is created for $\langle dx \ dx \rangle$ by using $d(x,t) = \text{density}(x,t) = \exp(\text{entropy}/k)$. This is then expanded to second order in dx creating a Gaussian distribution with a variance of:

$$- \ 1/ \left\{ d/dx \ d/dx \ \ln(d(x,t)) \right\} \quad ((4))$$

A main feature of (2) is that $1/m \ d/dx \ d(x,t) \langle pp \rangle$ appears in the Liouville equation and this term ultimately represents KE ave when the equation is altered to create conservation of energy. Thus, $\langle pp \rangle$ is unknown, but by using the axiom of (2) and ((4)) one has $\langle pp \rangle = 1/\langle xx \rangle$.

(2) writes $d(x,t) = WW$, where W anticipates the wavefunction. (R is actually used instead of W in (2)). One sees that other terms in the Liouville-continuity equation which is set to 0 are of the form:

$$d(x,t) \frac{d}{dx} \{ \} = 0 \quad ((5))$$

Thus, one requires that $\frac{1}{m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} WW \ln(WW)$ be put in this form.

This leads to: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{1}{W} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ which is the quantum average kinetic energy.

We now try to argue that this result follows directly from the axiom of (2). In other words, we suggest that the axiom introduces quantum mechanics a priori because $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ are Fourier transforms of each other.

Analysis in terms of $\exp(ipx)$

We argue that if $P(p)$ is the Fourier transform of $P(x)$, then:

$$P(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a_1(p) \exp(ipx)$$

Now $P(x)$ is known to be a Gaussian, so the square root of a Gaussian is also a Gaussian, so

$$\sqrt{P(x)} = W(x) = \text{quantum wavefunction} = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$$

One may note that for a single p (constant) one has $\exp(ipx)$ such that $d(x,t)$ proportional to $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ seems to be a probability-like object linked to $d(x,t)=1$ which demonstrates p and so may be used to calculate the average momentum.

In particular, if a $V(x)$ is present, one may consider:

$$W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad \text{and use this to calculate average kinetic energy } ((2))$$

The question becomes: Why does one use the square root of $d(x,t)$? We suggest that it is because for a free particle $d(x,t) = 1$, no p appears, so $\exp(ipx)$ only is present in the "square root", so to speak.

(2) introduces an axiom which suggests that $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ are Gaussians and Fourier transforms of each other, so $\exp(ipx)$ is introduced. We suggest that this is the key element of the axiom of (2) and already contains the essence of quantum mechanics a priori.

The use of the Liouville-continuity equation essentially introduces a $\frac{1}{m} \frac{d}{dx} \langle pp \rangle$ term (linked to kinetic energy which essentially becomes kinetic when the Liouville-continuity equation is changed into a conservation of energy one, which could have been written a priori.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Liouville-continuity equation approaches introduce $p/m = d/dx$ partial $S(x,t)$ and that later dS/dt partial $= -E$. This leads to $S = -Et + px$, where E is the bound state energy and p the bound center-of-mass momentum (usually 0). Thus, $-Et + px$ should apply to a free particle as well. If one uses d/dt partial and d/dx partial to pull out $-E$ and p , as is done, one may use the eigenfunction, $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and derive the Schrodinger equation from this using conservation of energy. Thus, all Liouville -continuity equation approaches essentially assume quantum mechanics a priori. They, however, introduce what seem as different conditions to create the average kinetic energy, but these must all be consistent with the average kinetic energy ((2)) obtained using $\exp(ipx)$.

We examine one special case, namely that of (2). In (2), a fundamental axiom is presented with states that: $\langle ppx \rangle \langle xx \rangle = \hbar^2/4$. These are essentially variances and if $P(x)$ is a Gaussian and $P(p)$ its Fourier transform, this is satisfied. Thus, we argue that a priori, the notion of $\exp(ipx)$ and hence quantum mechanics is introduced. One does not require a Liouville-equation or extra calculations, although these are consistent with $\exp(ipx)$ as we show.

In particular, for a Gaussian, $P(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a_1(p)\exp(ipx)$ and the square root $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ as it is also a Gaussian. One may note that for one constant p , one has $\exp(ipx)$ in $W(x)$ such that $W^*(x)W(x) = 1 = d(x,t)$. Thus, we suggest using $W(x)$ to calculate average kinetic energy without any further assumptions, although the results in (2) lead to a consistent calculation. We suggest that this follows from quantum mechanics already being present in the axiom of (2) a priori. The Liouville-continuity equation does not do much more than reduce to a conservation of energy equation which could have been written a priori, we argue. Furthermore, $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ is already present by assuming $p(x,t), m = d/dx$ partial $S(x,t)$ with $S(x,t) = -Et + px$. Thus, any other ideas introduced in a Liouville-continuity equation must be consistent with this in order to obtain the Schrodinger equation.

References

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